

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

VARIOUS MODES OF CLINICAL PRESENTATION OF FALCIPARUM MALARIA

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Article Received: March 2019

Accepted: April 2019

Published: May 2019

Abstract:

Objective: The aim of this research work is to assess the various clinical presentations of malaria due to falciparum parasite.

Study Design: This was a descriptive research work.

Study Venue & Duration: This research work was conducted in Sheikh Zayed Medical College and Hospital Rahim Yar Khan and the duration of this research work was from September 2016 to January 2019.

Methodology: Total of three hundred and forty-eight hospitalized patients with febrile illness were under screening for parasite of malaria with the peripheral smear of blood. We diagnosed the positive smears of 122 patients. Total 102 patients were positive for *P. falciparum*, who were the part of this research work. We found eleven patients positive for *P. vivax* & three patients found with combination of *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax*. These patients were not the part of this research work. We gave the injections of quinine sulphate to the patients who were ill critically, remaining patients got halofantrine and/or artemether through oral way.

Results: There were total one hundred and eight patients who were positive in the blood smears. Among them 68.51% (n: 74) were male patients and 31.48% (n: 34) were female patients. We diagnosed high temperature in all the patients. We observed jaundice in 36.11% (n: 39), nausea in 29.62% (n: 32), pain in the abdomen cavity in 21.29% (n: 23), changed condition of consciousness in 24.07% (n: 26) patients, diarrhea in 8.33% (n: 9), cough was present in 7.4% (n: 8) & seizures in 1.85% (n: 2) patients. Out of total one hundred and eight patients, 20.37% (n: 22) patients appeared with the malaria of cerebral, 7.4% patients were available with the infection of the respiratory tract, 8.33% (n: 9) patients appeared with gastroenteritis, 8.33% (n: 9) were present with acute pancreatitis but amylase of serum and ultrasound of the abdomen cavity omitted the discovery of the acute pancreatitis. Total 5.55% (n: 6) appeared with acute hepatitis & failure of fulminant hepatic with increased levels of serum ammonia in 3.70% (n: 4) patients and 2.77% (n: 3) patients appeared with the acute failure of kidneys.

Conclusion: The occurrence of the malaria due to *P. Falciparum* was much high among the patients of this research work. There is a possibility of the prevalence of falciparum malaria in all the patients suffering from febrile illness even with different appearances of malaria.

KEY WORDS: *P. falciparum*, *P. vivax*, appearance, prevalence, occurrence, methodology.

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Please cite this article in press Muhammad Tahir Mehmood et al., *Various Modes Of Clinical Presentation Of Falciparum Malaria.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(05).

INTRODUCTION:

One of the leading causes of morbidity & mortality in the world is malaria. The results show the outcome of three hundred to five hundred millions new patients and 1.50 to 3.0 million mortalities every year [1]. The re-emergence of this diseases in the regions where it disappeared is increasing day by day. Every year, more than thirty thousand travelers from the well-developed countries appeared with the infection of this disease and it leads to the death of hundreds patients. The untreated infection has the ability to continue further. This is due to the determination of plasmodium falciparum for more than 1.50 years but normally it ends from 6 to 8 months. This Infection is also the reason of defensive immunity whose decay occur after many years if there is not occurrence of the infection again. The malaria due to falciparum malaria is main problem of health in our communities of Pakistan.

There are very high rate of mortalities and morbidities with various manifestations, different presentations are not uncommon, in fact more frequent. The occurrence of malaria is increasing from last twenty years in our country Pakistan [2]. The diversity of culture and poorness is the cause of different challenges [3]. This complication of malaria is very complicate, it has the ability to mimic various diseases and there are no proper clinical factors for diagnosis [4]. There is a variation of the clinical presentation of the P. falciparum among persons based on the parasite level & immunity status of the candidate. It is very easy to treat and diagnose some of the malaria presentation as high temperature, chills & rigors. Malaria due to falciparum is the disorder of many systems, it can have uncommon appearances with signs expressive of infections of upper & lower respiratory tract including acute injury of the lung [5], meningitis [6], hepatitis [7], gastroenteritis [8] and some other presentations [8]. Neuro-psychiatric signs, syndrome of Guillain-Barre [9] & psychosis [10] are also available in reports. Due to so much adversity in the clinical appearance, it is very important matter for the professionals. The peripheral smears of the blood are very helpful to decrease the rates of morbidity & mortality due to this disease which widespread because of malaria.

METHODOLOGY:

The duration of this research work was from September 2016 to January 2019 in Sheikh Zayed Medical College and Hospital Rahim Yar Khan. The screening of three hundred and forty-eight hospitalized patients due to high fever having more than twelve year of age carried out with the help of peripheral blood smear for the parasites of malaria. The range of the fever's duration was three to seventeen days before they got admission in the hospital. The patients found with smear positive for the parasite of plasmodium falciparum were the part of this research work.

There were 122 patients with smear positive, 9% (n: 11) patients found positive for P. vivax & 2.45% (n: 3) patients found with combination of P. vivax & P. falciparum, these patients were not the part of this research work. We study the 88.52% (n: 108) patients who were positive for only P. falciparum. The substitute diagnoses test of blood, urine and cultures of stools carried out. The tests for liver function, studies of viral markers, chest X-ray, and ultrasound of abdomen, computerized tomography of brain, level of serum ammonia and levels of serum amylase carried out when there was requirement. The patients suffering from TB, hepatitis due to different viruses and liver abscess were not the part of this research work. We used the SPSS software for the analysis of collected information.

RESULTS:

There were one hundred and eight patients of P. falciparum malaria in which 68.51% (n: 74) patients were males & 31.48% (n: 34) patients were females. The patients got admission due to high fever. Total 36.11% (n: 39) patients found with jaundice whereas 21.29% (n: 23) patients were available with the pain in their abdomen. Loose motion was another common feature present in 8.33% (n: 9) patients. Among these patients early medical identification was of gastroenteritis & viral hepatitis. Cough was present in 7.4% (n: 8) patients. History of seizure was present in 2 patients. We observed the less level of hemoglobin in 16.66% (n: 18) patients whereas 36.11% (n: 39) patients found with deranged liver function tests. The creatinine of serum was high in 2.77% (n: 3) patients as elaborated in Table-1.

Table-I: Laboratory Investigations

Abnormality	N=108	
	Patients	Percent
Plasmodium falciparum seen	108.0	100.00
Hb<10g/dl	18.0	16.66
Raised urea	22.0	20.00
Raised creatinine	3.0	2.77
Altered LFTs (Hepatocellular 09, Hemolytic 24)	39.0	36.11
Leukocytosis > 12000/ μ l	14.0	12.96

Medical assessments showed that twenty-nine patients found with hepatomegaly, splenomegaly was available in sixteen patients whereas sixteen patients were suffering from abdominal tenderness. Malaria of cerebral was available in 20.37% (n: 22) patients eight patients among them found with infection of lower tract of respiration. Total 8.33% (n: 9) patients appeared with abdomen pain whereas 3.7% (n: 4) patients were available with the failure of fulminant hepatic. Three patients of kidney failure were also present.

DISCUSSION:

The malaria because of *P. falciparum* is a disorder of many systems and is the cause of many other diseases. Apart from normal appearances, most of the patients were available with different presentations. Malaria of cerebral is very noticeable feature of severer malaria of *P. falciparum* [11]. Any of the patient with changed should get treatment for severe nature malaria. Bhalli has concluded that twenty six percent patients of cerebral malaria [12], in this research work, it was responsible for 20.37% patients. The acute injury of the lung is also a complication of malaria due to *P. falciparum* [5]. In youngsters, pulmonary edema is not very common. There is sequestration of moderate level in the pulmonary vasculature and the aggregation of leukocytes are very imminent in than vasculature of brain [13, 14].

We concluded that 7.4% patients suffering from malaria due to *P. falciparum* were available with infection of lower tract of respiration whereas 13.0% was in the report of Iqbal [15]. The pain of abdomen cavity is also very common in the patients of malaria. But in some geographical regions, diarrhea due to water are the most common presentation [11]. Malabsorption available in the malaria proposes decreased perfusion of splanchnic [16-18]. Bhalli concluded 10.80% patients suffering from diarrhea [12]. Sequestration was present re is hepatic decrease flow of blood [19-21]. There was not a clear diagnosis of malaria & hepatitis in the department of emergency [8]. It presents to own hemolytic, pattern of hepatocellular [11]. About 3.7% patients appeared with failure of fulminant hepatic. This appearance of this particular failure is very frequent in the countries of tropic [22-23]. In severe nature malaria of *P.*

falciparum, complication leads to hypo perfusion of kidneys [24]. The injury of kidneys is the result of tubular necrosis [25]. The failure of kidneys is also another abnormality of the malaria especially among adults [11]. Bhalli concluded the level of hemoglobin less than ten 10 g/dl in 10.50% patients whereas Hashmi concluded in twenty-four percent patients [26].

CONCLUSION:

There are a lot of representations of the malaria due to *P. falciparum* and this can mimic many other diseases as mentioned above. The professional in the field must be aware about these presentations to tackle the problem to decrease the morbidity as well as mortality rate.

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